

Satellite Remote Sensing and AI: Detection and Mapping of West Africa Seagrass

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We use machine learning with satellite remote sensing for the detection of seagrass meadows. We examine areas of seagrass on the coast of West Africa, picking sites in Mauritania, Senegal and Guinea Bissau with differing seagrass and water turbidity environments. Verification of seagrass presence was supported by boat-based seafloor grab samples, scuba observations and sonar surveys. Various types of machine learning were applied to satellite imagery for detecting seagrass and other coastal habitat types, as well as for mapping the extent of the inter-tidal zone. Large areas can be mapped by satellite imagery, at low cost relative to other survey types. That provides a useful diagnostic of regional seagrass extent, from which changes over time can be monitored.

1 Introduction

This paper will address the application of satellite remote sensing with AI to detect areas of seagrass. Seagrass meadows are a critical ecosystem: they provide a valuable carbon sink (Duarte et al., 2013); they help purify seawater (Trégarot et al., 2018); they provide protection against coastal erosion (Lamb et al., 2017); and they provide a nursery for many species of fish (Trégarot et al., 2020).

Seagrass meadows are found in shallow coastal areas as they require light for photosynthesis, with many forming in the inter-tidal zone between high and low tides and others living at depths up to 50 meters (Kirkman & Walker, 1989). Seagrass meadows, are mostly confined to temperate or tropical zones and cover about 10% of the world's coastal areas (Hily & Job, 2015; UNEP & Short, 2018).

Despite their global importance, seagrass meadows face numerous threats from human sources (Unsworth et al., 2019). These include pollution from agricultural, domestic, and industrial sources, which

undermine their structure, stability, and functioning. Additionally, pressures from coastal exploitation, nutrient runoff, and climate change have led to a continued global decline in seagrass meadow areas, with a 7% global annual loss, equivalent to a football field every 30 minutes (UNDP-UNEP-WCMC, 2020).

Satellite images can be valuable to detect and monitor coastal ecosystems, including seagrass (Hossain et al., 2015). Seagrass distributions have been successfully mapped with aerial photos and satellite images with pixel sizes of 10m or less, while more recently drone remote sensing has mapped coastal ecosystems in cm-detail (Lyons et al., 2011; Kovacs et al., 2018). Satellites have many major advantages over both aircraft and drones, notably: better continuity of data collection, with some satellite data archives spanning many decades; satellites can also provide a better synoptic overview of habits, even whole ecosystems, relative to the limited views from aircraft or drones. Earth Observation (EO) data provide repeat-coverage, thematically consistent and spatially continuous measurements of ecosystems, their patterns and processes, with global coverage.

We present case studies on the use of satellite imagery to detect and characterise seagrass meadows in West Africa. In section 2 we discuss the importance of seagrass meadows in West Africa specifically. In section 3 we discuss the satellite remote sensing data, regression tree analysis and the importance of "ground truth" verification with drone, boat, scuba and sonar sources; in 4 we apply a neural network to determine the extent of the inter-tidal zones around the islands of Guinea Bissau and we conclude (section 5) with a summary of the usefulness of AI and space data in monitoring these critical coastal regions.

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2 West African seagrass meadows

In West Africa, seagrass meadows have been observed along the seven coastal countries (Mauritania, Senegal, Cape Verde, Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Guinea, and Sierra Leone), with three species (*Cymodocea nodosa*, *Zostera noltii*, and *Halodule wrightii*) in the south but only one species in the north (*Halodule wrightii*). The Cabo Verde archipelago hosts a further species, *Ruppia maritima* (De Los Santos et al., 2022).

Little research had been undertaken as to the extent and importance of this critical resources along the vast West African coastline. To highlight their importance and to counter the threats which are facing seagrass meadows they must be mapped.

In this study 4 areas of seagrass meadows are examined: Banc d'Arguin National Park in Mauritania, two sites in Senegal (Joal and the Delta du Saloum), and the Bijagos archipelago in Guinea Bissau. The locations of those areas are shown in figure 1 and discussed briefly below.

2.1 Mauritania: Banc d'Arguin National Park

The Banc Arguin National Park in Mauritania has so far been the best studied region for mapping and monitoring the health of seagrasses in west Africa (Touron-Gardic et al., 2022). It was thus used as a test region for this study.

2.2 Senegal: Joal and Delta du Saloum

We concentrate on two Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in Senegal; Joal and the Delta du Saloum. Joal is particularly important as this region has an extensive dataset of seagrass survey data reaching back to 2009. This ground truth data was collected via a boat-based seafloor grab-sample survey, covering 220 km², with a 500m × 500m grid (Mériaux & Sémelin, 2014). Updating this historic dataset, we also carried out sonar surveys, scuba sampling and underwater photography in the Joal area.

2.3 Guinea Bissau: the Bijagos Archipelago

The Bijagos Archipelago MPA in Guinea Bissau is particularly interesting because it has a species of seagrass which forms small clusters of seagrass, rather than meadows, in a district that has high levels of turbidity due to a deltaic setting. Such an area presents challenges for seagrass mapping from space. Extensive sonar surveys, verified by scuba sampling and underwater photography, were used here to verify the EO-based mapping of the seagrass occurrences.

Figure 1: Regions of the West African coast that this paper is centred on. The regions are described in section 2 and chosen due to the abundance of data available and access to ground truthing.

3 Classification and regression trees: mapping seagrass

Sentinel-2 (spatial resolution 10m) and PlanetScope (spatial resolution 3m) imaging were used in this analysis. Criteria for selecting images was that they were mostly cloud-free and from the lowest tidal period. This minimises the absorption of spectral wavelengths by water, assisting feature identification (Pottier et al., 2021).

The methodology used in this project builds on that developed by Pottier et al. (2021). The satellite images (Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope) were pre-processed for atmospheric and radiometric corrections. The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) were then calculated. Those two indices use specific spectral bands of the satellite sensors in order to mask and discriminate the water bodies (sub-tidal and intertidal), the land (terrestrial) and the transition zone between the marine and terrestrial coverage, consisting of mangroves, salt marshes, aquatic vegetation and mudflats (illustrated in the Banc d'Arguin test region, see Figure 2).

Next, a classification process of the satellite images took place by using the Classification and Regression Trees (CART) analysis, based on Decision Trees (Breiman et al, 1984). Decision Trees are important for classification and regression predictive modelling

Figure 2: Sentinel-2 based habitat mapping in the Banc d'Arguin test region using CART processing; green shades = seagrass.

in Machine Learning. CART analysis is a procedure where decision trees models are built according to the provided training data. Decision Trees can be used for classification to predict what group each pixel of the satellite image belongs to and for regression to predict a continuous value across the image, while also providing insights about the relationship of the dependent and independent variables. With 'Classification Trees' the target variable is categorical and the tree is used to identify the class within which a target variable would likely fall into. With 'Regression Trees' the target variable is continuous and the tree is used to predict its value. The final outcome classification products were further processed with a majority filter in order to eliminate any noisy isolated pixels.

For sites with no published maps and no/minimal marine 'ground-truth' reference data, the ratio of blue and red bands (Blue/Red) was used to detect potential marine substrates and vegetation types. Visual image analysis was also used, with PlanetScope and Google Earth archive satellite imagery from the past 20 years, hand-digitising seafloor geomorphological features to identify terrain likely to shelter and sustain seagrass.

3.1 The Banc d'Arguin test region

Figure 2 shows the marine and terrestrial habitats determined from Sentinel-2 multi-spectral images. The availability of low-tide ground-truth survey data highlights the extent of the seagrass meadows in this region. Our results are similar to a previous study using

Figure 3: Joal Marine Protected Area: comparison of the 2013 boat-based grab-sample results (500m x 500m grid sampling) with the 2020 PlanetScope-derived habitat map (3m x 3m pixels), for the distribution of seagrass (grid map source: Mériaux & Sémelin, 2014).

a Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm, to map the habitats (Pottier et al., 2021), but show a greater seagrass extent. Two further classifiers were tested: a Random Forest Classifier (RFC) with hyperparameters selected with grid-search cross-validation; and an Approximately Bayesian Neural Network (ABNN). The performance metrics for the RFC classifier are shown below, with the results for the ABNN being very similar:

Precision Train 0.877 Test 0.808
Recall Train 0.751 Test 0.589

3.2 Ground truthing satellite data

Ground truth references maps were built from multiple sources as mentioned in section 2. Whilst the ground truth data varies in quality and coverage there is good agreement between the satellite imaging analysis and the ground truth data. An example, for the Joal coast of Senegal, is shown in figure 3. PlanetScope imagery of this area was able to detect the inter-tidal and terrestrial habitat types, as well as the probable seagrass distribution and rocky sand coverage in the marine zone. That satellite-based mapping has excellent correlation with the 'ground-truth' reference maps from a 2009 boat-based seafloor grab-sample survey of seagrass and substrate (Mériaux & Sémelin, 2014).

In both the Senegal and Guinea Bissau surveys further ground truth data was provided by sonar and scuba measurements. Sonar data can provide precise bathymetry measurements which give valuable information on the geomorphology of the seafloor and the presence of seagrass (though multiple overlapping ground truth datasets are always advised). For example the E1 and E2 indices, which characterise the roughness and hardness of the acoustic signal has been used to differentiate seagrass from other seabed types, as shown in Figure 4 (e.g. Kloser et al., 2001;

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